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**ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE OF CARBON PRICING:
A CASE STUDY ON SINGAPORE'S CARBON TAX IMPLEMENTATION**

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Anita Fernandez Rios

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CPA – Carbon Pricing Act

CO₂ – Carbon Dioxide

CT – Carbon Tax

ETS – Emission Trading System

EU – European Union

FPCC – Fixed-price carbon credits

GHG – Greenhouse gas

GWP – Global Warming Potential

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

MSE – Ministry of Sustainability and Environment

NCCS – National Climate Change Secretariat

NEA – National Environment Agency

REACH – Reaching Everyone for Active Citizenry@Home

SMEs – Small and Medium Enterprises

“tCO₂e” – means metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalence

UNFCCC – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

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Abstract

Carbon pricing has emerged as a crucial strategy for abating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and climate change. Numerous jurisdictions across the globe have embraced carbon pricing mechanisms to incentivize emission reductions. Singapore introduced its Carbon Pricing Act in 2018, the first in Southeast Asia.

Under this Act, facilities directly emitting 25,000 tons of greenhouse gases or more were required to pay a carbon tax rate set at S\$5 per ton of CO₂ equivalent (tCO₂e) from 2019 to 2023. This initial rate allowed companies emitting GHGs to adjust gradually. Subsequently, the tax rate increased to S\$25/tCO₂e for 2024-2025 and further to S\$45/tCO₂e by 2026 to 2027. There is an indication that the tax rate could reach between S\$50 and S\$80 per tCO₂e by 2030.

Implementing a carbon policy presented several critical challenges. These included determining the optimal carbon price level to effectively incentivize emission reductions, ensuring equitable distribution of the burden and benefits, and establishing mechanisms to protect vulnerable groups disproportionately affected by the policy. Simultaneously, the policy aimed to foster the growth and competitiveness of the local economy.

This case study on the Environmental Governance of Carbon Pricing: Carbon Tax Implementation in Singapore, examined Singapore's carbon pricing journey using Bennett and Satterfield's environment governance criteria. The results revealed that environmental governance has been effective, equitable, responsive, and robust. However, there is room for improvement regarding fairness, justice, and stakeholder participation. Recommendations include enhancing participation levels, increasing transparency, and ensuring a fair distribution of benefits. Further studies are

recommended to assess the overall impact of an improved ecosystem resulting from effective environmental governance.

Keywords: Carbon pricing, Carbon Tax, Climate change, Environmental Governance

I. INTRODUCTION

Global warming is a pressing global issue that requires urgent action due to its significant effect on changing global climate. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) unequivocally asserted that greenhouse emissions from human activities have significantly increased the Earth's global surface temperature. Between 2011 and 2020, these emissions caused the global temperature to rise by more than 1.1°C above pre-industrial levels. This increase is primarily due to greenhouse gases (GHG), such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane, chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), and nitrous oxide. Notably, CO₂ alone accounts for more than half of the enhanced greenhouse effect (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2021).

Over the past two decades, initiatives to curb greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions have been in effect worldwide. These efforts encompass various strategies, such as enhancing energy efficiency in transportation, buildings, and industrial operations, promoting energy-efficient appliances, and divesting from fossil industries. Additionally, numerous countries have shifted toward renewable and clean energy sources, launched afforestation and reforestation programs, embraced circular economy practices, and prioritized sustainable agriculture. Recently, carbon capture and storage have also gained attention. Despite these endeavors, it is evident that further action is necessary to address the climate crisis.

Singapore recognizes the critical importance of reducing greenhouse gas emissions as climate change impacts threaten the nation's coastal infrastructure, ecosystems, and economy. Rising sea levels, increasing temperatures, and changing weather patterns necessitate actions to build resilience. Additionally, Singapore is committed to global efforts. As a signatory to the Paris Agreement, the nation pledged

to limit its contribution to global warming (National Climate Change Secretariat [NCCS], n.d.c).

As part of its overall Singapore Green Plan 2030, Singapore implemented Carbon Pricing, the first in Southeast Asia, as one of the key strategies to reduce GHG emissions. The imposition of a carbon tax underpins its net zero target by making producers and consumers responsible and accountable for the GHG emission of production, transportation, energy usage, and other processes that emit greenhouse gases.

The initial carbon tax rate was set at S\$5/tCO_{2e} for the first five years from 2019 to 2023 to allow companies emitting GHGs a transition period to adjust. This tax rate was increased in succeeding years, with a projected higher tax rate by 2030 (NCSS, n.d.a).

Baranzini et al. (2017) cautioned implementors that the challenges of carbon tax are implementation and determining the appropriate tax rate that effectively reduces emissions without causing undue burden on businesses and individuals. To do this, countries must carefully consider the socio-economic impacts of the tax and determine how the revenue will be used.

Singapore's carbon pricing strategy is not without criticism and scrutiny from various sectors. Tseng (2022), a research fellow of the Faculty of Law at the National University of Singapore, conducted a study to review Singapore's carbon tax against the backdrop of sustainability. He cited that while the Carbon Tax policy in Singapore is a 'step in the right direction,' it is highly influenced by economic priorities and could undermine the primary objectives of carbon reduction in the long term.

The Climate Action Tracker (2022) has rated Singapore's performance as "Critically insufficient". In its update, CAT stated:

In November 2022, a few days prior to COP27, Singapore submitted its updated NDC, setting a new target of limiting GHG emissions in 2030 to 60 MtCO_{2e}, down from 65 Mt CO_{2e} in the previous submission. While the target is stronger in absolute number, it is only a marginal improvement over the last, and it is still far higher than 1.5°C levels. Singapore’s overall CAT rating remains unchanged at “Critically insufficient.”

In reply, Minister for Sustainability and the Environment Grace Fu said on January 9, 2023, during a Parliament hearing, that Singapore was aware of CAT’s assessment of its climate action policies. Despite significant improvements over the past year, including updated commitments, a net-zero target, and other initiatives, CAT’s latest rating for Singapore’s “policies and plans” remains puzzlingly low. Minister Grace Fu said that CAT’s assessment needs to fully consider Singapore’s circumstances, one being that it has very limited access to alternative energy sources (Fu, 2023).

The National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) has sought clarifications from CAT regarding its methodology, however as of January 5, 2023, no response has been received yet.

One can also refer to the World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicators. While not specific to the environmental governance of GHG emission, this information can shed light on the quality of governance in Singapore. World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicators collect data on governance quality from households, businesses, and citizens across more than 200 countries and territories. Over a ten-year period, the results consistently rate Singapore highly (close to 100%) in areas such as Political Stability, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law,

and Control of Corruption. However, the rating for Voice and Accountability remains consistently low, typically falling in the 50-60% range (World Bank Group, n.d.).

While these critics did not intend to undermine Singapore's climate action efforts through a carbon tax, their critiques inadvertently spurred the government to take decisive actions.

Conducting an assessment based on well-defined governance criteria can assist policymakers in refining their policies and implementation strategies. Objectively examining Singapore's carbon pricing journey using a set of criteria allows us to identify areas for potential improvement.

The carbon pricing policy in Singapore raises specific considerations. Firstly, it is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of the carbon pricing policy in achieving its intended goals. Assessments should include an analysis of whether the carbon price is set at an appropriate level to incentivize emission reductions and whether the policy is being enforced effectively, including the potential interactions and synergies between carbon pricing and other climate policies in Singapore. Furthermore, the assessment should also consider the fairness and equity of the carbon pricing policy, whether the burden and benefits of the carbon price are distributed equitably among different industries and sectors, and whether mechanisms are in place to ensure that vulnerable groups are not disproportionately affected by the policy.

The governance assessment should also evaluate the transparency and accountability of the carbon pricing policy and include an examination of how the carbon pricing policy is developed and implemented, stakeholder engagement and participation in the policy development and implementation process, the impact of the policy on economic competitiveness and job creation, and the potential for unintended consequences or market distortions and finally, whether there is a robust monitoring

and reporting system to ensure compliance and integrity of emissions data (World Bank et al., 2016).

The governance assessment of Singapore's carbon pricing policy should examine its effectiveness, fairness, transparency, and accountability to ensure its successful implementation and contribution to reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Carbon Pricing

The global efforts to reduce greenhouse emissions have become increasingly important in addressing the urgent issue of climate change (Aldy & Stavins, 2012). One of the key strategies used in these efforts is carbon pricing. Carbon Pricing is the implementation of a cost on carbon emissions, either through a Carbon Tax or an Emission Trading System (Baranzini et al., 2017). Carbon Pricing is widely regarded as an efficient method to address the economic problem of greenhouse gas emissions being a negative externality. Carbon Pricing makes it costly to emit greenhouse gases, therefore driving individuals and companies to take action to reduce carbon emissions.

The more common forms of carbon pricing are Carbon Taxes and Emission Trading schemes. Boyce (2018) defines carbon tax as a direct price on each ton of carbon dioxide emitted. The government typically determines this tax and can vary depending on the level of emissions. On the other hand, an emission trading scheme involves creating a market for carbon allowances or permits. These permits allow businesses and organizations to emit a certain amount of greenhouse gases, which can be bought or sold in a regulated market. While both carbon taxes and emission trading schemes are forms of carbon pricing, there are some key differences between the two (Aldy and Stavins, 2012).

Carbon taxes are levies placed on the amount of carbon dioxide emissions produced by businesses, industries, and individuals. They provide a direct price signal on carbon emissions, encouraging emitters to reduce their emissions. On the other hand, Emission Trading Systems establish a cap on total emissions and allocate allowances that can be bought and sold among participants. Participants can trade

these allowances to meet their emission reduction targets. For example, a company that emits less than its allocated allowances can sell its surplus to another company that exceeds its allowances. Both carbon taxes and emission trading schemes aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by making it more costly for businesses and individuals to emit carbon dioxide (Boyce, 2018).

Boyce (2018) elaborated that it is easier to implement carbon pricing where fossil fuels enter the economy at ports, pipeline terminals, and from mines. Under this system, for every ton of CO₂ that will be emitted when the fuel is burned, the supplier pays a tax or surrender a permit. This approach covers all sources of carbon entering the jurisdiction. Another approach is called midstream compliance or point source emission. Entities such as power plants, carbon-intensive industrial facilities, or fossil fuel distributors are covered. Midstream systems or point sources are typically less comprehensive than upstream systems because they do not cover all sectors. Singapore's carbon pricing scheme is applied to the midstream use of fossil fuel.

Carbon Pricing Uptake

Over the past decade, carbon markets and mechanisms have undergone significant evolution, as highlighted in the World Bank's State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2023. The report indicated record-high revenues from both carbon tax and ETS. That amount is about \$95 USD billion despite a backdrop of high inflation, fiscal pressures, and energy crises. The number of jurisdictions (Figure 1) has likewise increased. Seventy-four (74) carbon pricing instruments now cover twenty-three percent (23%) of global GHGs; 37 ETS and 37 Carbon Tax.

Figure 1. Global GHG emissions covered by ETSs and carbon taxes (World Bank, 2023).

High-income countries still dominate the uptake of ETS and carbon taxes; however, new economies are following suit. Mexico, Austria and Indonesia plan to implement these instruments and in sub-national jurisdictions in USA. Other countries like Chile, Malaysia, Vietnam, Thailand, and Turkey are working towards implementing direct carbon pricing.

In summary, the report highlighted that in addition to raising revenue, driving innovation, and facilitating international trade, Carbon Pricing delivers a wider and more sustained sustainability and development goals (World Bank, 2023).

The World Bank’s 2023 report (Figure 2) revealed the current carbon prices for countries implementing carbon taxes, expressed in US dollars. Notably, Uruguay has

the highest rate at \$156 per ton of CO₂, while Ukraine has the lowest rate at \$0.82 per ton of CO₂. However, it is essential to recognize that these figures serve as approximations, influenced by variations in the scope of greenhouse gas emissions covered by carbon taxation (World Bank, 2023).

Figure 2. Carbon tax rates - World Bank 2023 report.

Experiences in Other Countries

Among the seven (7) highly industrialized countries, only Canada, France, Japan, and the United Kingdom have implemented a carbon tax. Italy, Germany, and the USA (with the exception of certain federal jurisdictions) have opted for alternative mechanisms to reduce carbon emissions (Santikarn et al., 2021).

- **Canada:** British Columbia's carbon tax, implemented in 2008, gained international acclaim as a model for carbon taxation, significantly reducing the level of GHG, but it was anticipated that the carbon price would increase. British Columbia's approach covered 70% of provincial GHG emissions from both household and industrial fossil fuel consumption fairly (Harrison, 2019). The gradual and predictable tax increase from \$10 per ton of CO₂ in 2008 to \$30 per ton in 2012 followed expert recommendations. Tax revenues were then allocated as low-income dividends to prevent economic impact on low-income households and as offset to individual and corporate income tax. Strong political leadership was a prime factor for the continued use of CT as a GHG reduction measure (Harrison, 2019).
- **France:** France introduced a carbon tax in 2014 to reduce emissions and promote cleaner energy sources. The majority of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from CO₂ emissions are related to energy use (approximately 72%). As of 2021, these emissions were subject to pricing mechanisms, including fuel excise taxes, carbon taxes, and participation in the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS). Nearly 90% of France's carbon emissions from energy use are priced, with approximately 43% falling within an Effective Carbon Rate (ECR) or Carbon Tax exceeding EUR 60 per ton of CO₂. These higher-priced emissions primarily originate from the road transport and industrial sectors (OECD,

2023). Protests and social unrest occurred due to perceived unfairness and economic burden on certain groups, and the Government needed to enhance communication about the tax's purpose and benefits and consider CO₂ measures to alleviate the impact on vulnerable populations.

- **Japan:** In 2012, Japan introduced a carbon tax that covered 75% of its emissions, which is 1.72% of global emissions. The goal was to distribute a fair and economy-wide burden on fossil fuel use based on their CO₂ content, promoting a decarbonized society and bolstering climate change mitigation efforts. The tax applies to CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion across all sectors, with some exemptions to maintain competitiveness. Upstream fossil fuel producers are responsible for paying this tax, and the effective carbon rate (ECR) exceeds EUR 60 per ton of CO₂ (OECD, 2023).

- **United Kingdom (UK):** The UK's carbon price support tax aims to enhance investment economics and reduce revenue uncertainty for low-carbon energy generation within the UK's electricity sector. This tax was introduced due to the instability, uncertainty, and insufficient pricing of European Union Allowances (EUAs) to encourage significant investment in low-carbon electricity production. Following the UK's exit from the EU and the establishment of the UK Emissions Trading System (UK ETS), the UK government confirmed that the power sector would continue participating in the Carbon Price Support (CPS). The minimum carbon price remains at GBP 18 per ton of CO₂ equivalent between 2021 and March 2024, with future rates yet to be announced. The tax will persist until unabated coal-fired power generation is phased out, with the Government committed to ending unabated coal use by October 2024 (OECD, 2023).

- **Indonesia:** Indonesia is actively addressing its commitments under the Paris Agreement through significant legislative developments. Two crucial initiatives are underway: the Omnibus Bill and Carbon Tax and a draft Presidential Regulation and Emissions Reduction Framework. The new legislation outlines how a carbon tariff would be implemented sometime in 2024 or 2025. Balancing economic development with environmental goals remains challenging, and this has hindered the implementation of the carbon tax law (Teja, 2023).
- **Australia:** Although carbon pricing has been extensively debated for over a decade, its initial implementation in Australia was brief due to political disagreements. Initially introduced by the Gillard government in 2012, it faced opposition from the Abbott government, which in 2014 swiftly replaced it with a \$3 billion taxpayer subsidy for applicants promising carbon emission reductions. Despite this short-lived implementation, Australia did experience a decrease in CO₂ emissions. Unfortunately, political considerations overshadowed scientific reasoning during that period. After another decade, and recent global developments, Australia decided to reinstate carbon pricing. Following the EU's announcement of its Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), and the United States' similar actions, Australia reintroduced the carbon tax on July 1, 2023, to cushion the economic impacts of Australia's exports to the EU and the US. Under this renewed approach, fossil fuel operations, mines, refineries, and smelters must reduce emissions intensity by 5% annually through absolute reductions or buy carbon offsets (Morton, 2023).

Overall, carbon taxes are now implemented in several countries, but challenges persist. Policymakers must balance environmental goals, economic impacts, and social equity to ensure effective carbon pricing strategies.

Singapore's Carbon Pricing Policy (CPA 2018)

The main policy driving carbon pricing is the Carbon Pricing Act (CPA), which was enacted in 2018 and took effect on January 1, 2019. Administered by the National Environment Agency (NEA), the CPA 2018 specifically mandates the reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and the payment of taxes related to these emissions. The Act builds upon an existing Energy Conservation Act (ECA) 2012, which is also administered by the same national agency. The Energy Conservation Act requires companies to promote energy conservation, improve energy efficiency, and reduce environmental impact as part of their energy efficiency and management practices. (Allen and Gledhill, 2019).

The CPA 2018 ("Carbon Pricing Act 2018," 2020) outlines the scope of its application, mandating that individuals and business establishments register and report their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The CPA 2018 applies to facilities in these industry sectors:

1. Manufacturing and manufacturing-related services,
2. Supply of electricity, gas, steam, compressed air, and chilled water for air conditioning, and
3. Water supply and sewage and waste management.

Key greenhouse gases (GHGs) covered under the CPA 2018 are found in Schedule 1 of the CPA including carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), Nitrous Oxide (N₂O), Sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆), Nitrogen Trifluoride (NF₃); Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), and Perfluorocarbons (PFCs).

Part 3 of the Act specifies the requirements for registration: individuals must register as 'registered persons' while business facilities need to register as 'reportable facilities' and 'taxable facilities'. These registrations are contingent upon the level of reckonable GHG emissions. Reckonable GHG emissions are defined in the First Schedule of the CPA 2018. Facilities emitting GHG emissions of 2,000 tCO_{2e} or more are obligated to report their annual emissions, while facilities emitting 25,000 t CO_{2e} or more are mandated to pay carbon tax.

Emissions reports described in Part 4 of the CPA 2018 require that the reports be based on approved monitoring plans, completed according to approved calculations and emissions factors, and verified by an external and independent assessor.

The Carbon Pricing (Measurement, Reporting and Verification) Regulations 2018, which also took effect on January 1, 2019, defines the details of monitoring plans, manner of calculations and verification process.

Specific to carbon tax is Part 5, Division 1, Section 16 which contains details of carbon tax measurement, verification and payments. The carbon tax is charged based on the total amount of reckonable GHG emissions in any year of a business facility that is a taxable facility. The initial carbon tax rate was at S\$5/tCO_{2e} for the first five years starting in 2019 to allow a transition period for companies emitting GHG to implement reduction measures. This tax rate was increased to S\$25/tCO_{2e} for the years 2024 to 2025 and S\$45/tCO_{2e} from 2026 to 2027 with the approval of the Carbon Pricing Act 2022, effective January 1, 2024. Carbon tax payments are made by the surrender of fixed-price carbon credits (FPCC) purchased at the specified carbon tax rates from the NEA.

The CPA also provides for de-registration of facilities due to closure or reduced operation and appeals.

Two other subordinate regulations were promulgated in support of superior law CPA 2018. These are Carbon Pricing (Registration and General Matters) Regulations 2018 and Carbon Pricing (Composition of Offences) Regulations 2018. All these laws came into effect on the same day as the CPA 2018, which is January 1, 2019. (“Carbon Pricing Act 2018: Subsidiary Legislation,” 2024).

Measurement, Reporting and Verification (MRV)

The NEA ensures that all emission reports are accurate, credible, and verifiable. The reports must also comply with UNFCCC guidelines in reporting GHG emissions (National Economic Agency [NEA], n.d.a).

The CPA 2018, as amended in 2022, required the measurement and reporting of GHG emissions according to the requirements of the Carbon Pricing (Measurement, Reporting and Verification) Regulations 2018. These are Scope 1 emissions or GHG directly released into the atmosphere from fuel combustion and Industrial Processes and Product Use (IPPU) activities within the business facility.

There are two emissions thresholds with specific requirements as listed in Table 1.

Table 1

Emissions Threshold (NEA, n.d.a)

First emissions threshold – Facility emits between $\geq 2,000$ and $< 25,000$ tCO ₂ e in any calendar year (tCO ₂ e/year)	Second emissions threshold – Facility emits between $\geq 25,000$ tCO ₂ e in any calendar year (tCO ₂ e/year)
Register as a reportable facility	Register as a taxable facility

Submit an annual Emissions Report	Submit a Monitoring Plan
No carbon tax liability	Submit an annual third-party verified Emissions Report
	Pay carbon tax for the verified reckonable emissions in the Emissions Report

The CPA defines GHG emissions as subject to carbon tax. These are called 'Reckonable' emissions. Reckonable emissions are "all direct emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFCs, and PFCs from fuel combustion, industrial processes and product use (IPPU), excluding emissions defined as non-reckonable." CH₄ and N₂O emissions from combustion of biofuels or biomass are also included as Reckonable emissions. Appendix A is a complete list of GHG covered under CPA 2018.

The NEA Carbon Tax website provides a downloadable Excel spreadsheet for calculating GHG emissions. Appendix B shows an extract of a portion of the excel spreadsheet.

NEA Verification Requirement

Emissions reports are prepared based on an NEA-approved monitoring plan and verified by an NEA-accredited independent verifier prior to its submission to NEA. The independent verifier must meet NEA accreditation requirements of Carbon Pricing (Measurement, Reporting and Verification) Regulations 2018, namely:

- must have a good understanding of industrial GHG processes and measurement within the facility, including potential emission sources,
- must have sufficient experience in GHG emissions verification in a jurisdiction requiring GHG measurement and reporting,

- must be knowledgeable of computational methodologies for emission sources and GHG specified in relevant international standards or guidelines, e.g., ISO14064, and have a good understanding of Singapore's regulatory requirements relating to GHG measurement, reporting, and verification, and
- must have the ability to assess the scope of verification activities necessary to substantiate a reasonable level of assurance ("Carbon Pricing Act 2018," 2020).

Other Policies with Requirements on Climate Action (“Carbon Pricing Act 2018: Subsidiary Legislation,” 2024).

The following are other policies and regulations in Singapore with requirements supporting the Singapore Green Plan and Carbon Pricing Act.

- Environmental Protection and Management Act 1999, EPM (Air Impurities) Regulations, and EPM (Greenhouse Gases) Regulations 2022
- Energy Conservation Act 2012 and Energy Management Practices Regulations 2013
- Energy Conservation (Fuel Economy and Vehicular Emissions Labelling) Regulations 2012
- Energy Conservation (Greenhouse Gas Measurement and Reporting) Regulations 2017
- Carbon Pricing Act 2018 & Carbon Pricing (Measurement, Reporting and Verification) Regulations 2018
- Regulations for Mandatory Climate-Related Disclosures (CRD) introduced by the Accounting and Corporate Regulatory Authority (ACRA) and Singapore Exchange Regulations on Feb 28, 2024.

Structural Arrangement to Implement the Carbon Pricing Policy

Singapore is a sovereign, democratic state with a written constitution forming the supreme law of the land. The Constitution defines the fundamental principles and basic framework for the Executive, Legislative, and Judiciary branches of the state. The legislative branch, comprising of the President and elected members of the Parliament, is responsible for enacting legislation, while the Executive branch, led by the Prime Minister, comprising of Cabinet members, is responsible for the general

direction of the Government and accountable to Parliament. The cabinet is the central decision-making body of the executive branch. The Judiciary, on the other hand, is an independent body responsible for interpreting the law and administering justice through its courts in accordance with the Constitution (Prime Minister's Office Singapore, n.d.).

The administration and enforcement of the Carbon Pricing Act of 2018 are placed under the National Environment Agency (NEA), a statutory board under the Ministry of Sustainability and the Environment. Carbon pricing is just one of the many measures the Singapore government has undertaken to tackle climate change. A secretariat, the National Climate Change Secretariat, with its website, was established on July 1, 2010, under the office of the Prime Minister to develop and implement Singapore's domestic and international policies and strategies to tackle climate change. It is the Government's 'think tank' on climate change issues (NCCS, n.d.b).

The National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) plays a crucial role in promoting carbon emission reduction across all sectors, supporting Singapore's adaptation to climate change impacts, capitalizing on economic and sustainable growth opportunities related to climate change action, and fostering public awareness and engagement in issues related to climate change.

In addition, an Inter-Ministerial Committee on Climate Change (IMCC) was created to strengthen a whole-of-government approach and coordination on climate change policies. The IMCC is led by the Senior Minister and Coordinating Minister for National Security. The IMCC is composed of an Executive Committee and working groups. Refer to Figure 3 for the structure of the IMCC (NCCS, n.d.b).

Figure 3. The IMCC and its sub-committees.

The NCCS website contains information on the delineation of each of these working groups, such as:

1. **The Carbon & Energy Transition Working Group (CETWG)** oversees the development, implementation, and tracking of progress for carbon mitigation measures. Its focus is on transitioning to cleaner energy sources, reducing carbon emissions, and promoting sustainable practices.
2. **The Economic Transition Working Group (ETWG)** is responsible for coordinating the growth of Singapore's green economy.
3. **The Resilience Working Group (RWG)** investigates effects of climate change on Singapore and recommends long-term resilience plans.
4. **The Sustainability & Engagement Working Group (SEWG)** takes care of the national sustainability agenda and emerging sustainability issues. The SEWG is also responsible for local and internationally related to climate change and sustainability.

In addition to government institutions, private and non-governmental groups, industry associations, financial institutions, and academia all contributed to the development of CPA 2018 and supported its implementation. Appendix G contains a list of private sector organizations supporting climate action and carbon pricing in Singapore.

Processes for Policy Creation, Negotiation, Conflict Resolution and Decision-making

Singaporean laws are established by the Parliament and are referred to as 'Acts of Parliament'. Any member of Parliament has the authority to propose a bill, which then undergoes a sequence of readings and discussions before receiving approval from the President. Once approved, the law is officially notified by publication in the Government Gazette. Figure 4 below shows stages in consideration of Bills and actions on debates and decision-making (Parliament of Singapore, n.d.).

Figure 4. Principal stages in the consideration of Bills in the Parliament of Singapore.

Legislative History of the Carbon Pricing Act

The following events occurred according to the legislative process when applied to the Carbon Pricing Act 2018 and its subsequent amendments.

Table 2

Legislative History of CPA 2018 (“Carbon Pricing Act 2018,” 2020)

Date	Legislative procedures
2 March, 2018	First Reading- Carbon Pricing Bill; Introduction of CPA 2018
20 March, 2018	Second Reading – Presentation on the general principles and merits of the Bill
	Committee Stage- The Committee reviews the details of the Bill.
	Third Reading – Third reading by the Parliament
Not published	PCMR review to ensure the Bill is not disadvantageous to persons of any racial or religious community.
11 April, 2018	The Act was approved by the President on 11 April 2018 to effect on Jan 1, 2019.
1 June, 2018	First published in the Government Gazette, Electronic Edition, on 1 June 2018 at 5 pm.
1 January 2019	Commencement of Carbon Pricing Act 2018.
1 January	Carbon Pricing Act 2018 (Amendment of Second Schedule)

Date	Legislative procedures
2021	Order 2021
7 October 2019	Act 40 of 2019—Supreme Court of Judicature (Amendment) Act 2019 (Amendments made on section 28(1) and item 16 of the Schedule to the Act)
5 November 2019	Commencement: 2 January 2021 Second Reading, Notice of Amendments, and Third Reading
2 Jan 2021	Commencement
12 October 2021	Carbon Pricing Act 2018 (Amendment of Fourth Schedule) Order 2021
31 December 2021	2020 Revised Edition—Carbon Pricing Act 2018 Operation
1 November 2022	Carbon Pricing Act 2018 (Amendment of Fourth Schedule) Order 2022
3 October 2022	First Reading of Act 37 of 2022—Carbon Pricing (Amendment) Act 2022 (Bill No. 27/2022)
8 November 2022	Second and Third Readings - Carbon Pricing (Amendment) Act 2022 (Bill No. 27/2022)
1 January 2024	Date of Commencement of Carbon Pricing Act 2022

Debates and Consultations

Fora and public consultations occurred as early as March 2015. An online consultation process was initiated by the NCCS to seek suggestions and feedback from private and people sectors on Singapore's on Climate Change Strategy. The discussions covered various topics related to carbon efficiency and energy conservation in Singapore. These included energy-efficient homes, carbon efficiency in transportation, renewable and clean energy for businesses, and efficiency measures in the power, waste, and water sectors. Additionally, closed-door stakeholder dialogues addressed specific issues (NCCS, 2015).

A consensus emerged that Singapore's primary strategy for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions remains centered on enhancing energy efficiency across

diverse sectors of the economy. This involves leveraging existing technologies while promoting behavioral changes in reducing energy utilization. Notably, there is growing interest in solar energy adoption, and the renewable energy industry is poised for growth, offering economic benefits. These collective efforts aim to align Singapore with its climate objectives, cut energy expenses, and foster new business prospects (NCCS, 2015).

It was during this consultation that carbon taxation or result-based carbon and co-benefit finance/trading to increase carbon abatement was suggested.

The Ministry of Sustainability and Water Resources (now Ministry of Environment and Sustainability), Minister Masagos Zulfiki (2018), has articulated to stakeholders the rationale for putting carbon pricing policy during the consultation process in March 2017, one year before the lodgment of the Carbon Pricing Bill in 2018. It was emphasized that carbon pricing complements Singapore's efforts to reduce emissions and meet its commitments to UNFCCC, increase energy efficiency, and incentivize clean technology and innovation (NCCS, 2017).

On March 20, 2018, during the second hearing of the CPA bill, Minister Masagos Zulfiki (2018) reiterated the importance and urgency of a carbon pricing bill and the imposition of a carbon tax on 80% of Singapore's GHG emissions. The design of the Singapore CPA took reference to EU and South Korea in deciding the threshold level of 25,000 tons annually (Zulfiki, 2018).

He emphasized that the CPA 2018 intends to incentivize behavior change. Carbon pricing establishes a price signal that encourages emitters to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Companies that emit GHG in Singapore do not bear a direct cost for emitting these harmful gases. CPA 2018 legislation addresses environmental concerns by holding accountable those who

contribute to greenhouse gas emissions. By implementing a carbon price, emitters will need to consider the cost of their emissions in their business decisions, leading to more conscious efforts to reduce emissions and energy consumption. Minister Zulfiki (2018) stated that carbon price would enable Singapore to reduce emissions in a cost-effective manner. Without a carbon price, reliance on regulations and other measures would likely be more expensive and disruptive for companies. Implementing a carbon price streamlines emission reduction efforts while minimizing economic impact.

The CPA serves as a platform to promote renewable energy and innovation. Introducing a carbon price stimulates demand for renewables and encourages technological advancements in energy efficiency and clean energy. Singapore has an opportunity in research and development of Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS). This fosters green growth opportunities within Singapore and globally as the world transitions toward resource-efficient and sustainable practices. Jurisdictions with a carbon price have successfully reduced emissions while maintaining economic growth, thus promoting environmental benefits (CNA, 2022).

Key Changes in the 2018 CPA

On November 8, 2022, during the Second Hearing of Act 37 of 2022 - Carbon Pricing (Amendment) Bill, Minister Grace Fu of the Ministry of Environment and Sustainability proposed increasing the carbon tax to S\$25 per ton for greenhouse gas emissions in 2024 and 2025, and S\$45 per ton for greenhouse gas emissions in 2026 and beyond (Fu, 2022).

Minister Grace Fu emphasized the urgency of addressing climate change, which many consider the greatest existential challenge to humanity. She cited the COP 27 report, highlighting that the world is not currently on track to meet the targets set in the Paris Agreement. To align with international commitments, Singapore aims to reduce its emissions to around 60 million tons by 2030 after peaking emissions earlier and achieve net zero emissions by 2050. The government estimates that emissions will peak between 2025 and 2028. Furthermore, Singapore is preparing for the EU's imposition of CO₂ emissions costs on specific imports, including steel, cement, fertilizers, aluminum, and electricity, starting in 2026 (CNA, 2022)

The amendment encompasses the following key points:

1. Defining broad parameters for the industry transition framework, which grants temporary allowances to companies in Emissions-Intensive Trade-Exposed or EITE sectors facing intense global competition.
2. The International Carbon Credits framework, or ICC framework, established under Sections 33A to 33D in Part 5 of the CPA, introduces tractable certificates representing emissions reductions or removal from projects or programs out of Singapore. Notably:
 - a. ICC must be capped at a facility-level limit of 5% of taxable emissions.

- b. This provision applies exclusively to carbon tax-liable companies surrendering credits for their carbon tax liabilities, rather than voluntary carbon footprint offsets.
3. The amendment also included an updated list of greenhouse gases (First and Second Schedule of the Act, particularly adding NF₃ or Nitrogen trifluoride, a chemical mostly used in the electronics industry and solar cells. It is hazardous to health and a GHG, with GWPs of NF₃ 16,800, 12, 200, and 18,700 for time horizons of 20, 100, and 500 years, respectively. This means that NF₃ is 16,800, 12,200, and 18,700 times more powerful than CO₂ in trapping atmospheric heat over a 20-, 100-, and 500-year timespan, respectively (Torres, n.d.)

Summary of Concerns on CPA 2018

The National Climate Change Secretariat, through the government's feedback unit known as 'Reaching Everyone for Active Citizenry @' (REACH), has organized multiple consultations on Singapore's climate change strategy, which included discussions about carbon pricing. During these consultations, the government engaged over 1,200 stakeholders from diverse segments of society, including youth, businesses, green groups, academe, and NGOs, as part of the Singapore Green Plan 2030 (NCCS, 2022).

In its public consultation on Singapore's Raised Climate Change Ambition held between Sept 5-26, 2022 (prior to the proposed Carbon Pricing Amendment Bill), 490 responses were received from members of the public, businesses, and Non-Government Organizations. The majority expressed the view that Singapore's climate change ambitions are not sufficiently ambitious, and that the country should enhance

its 2030 National Determined Contribution. Almost everyone (94%) agreed that there will be trade-offs, but they are willing to do their part to achieve the net-zero target. Respondents also supported further increasing the carbon price progressively to S\$50–\$80/tCO_{2e} by 2030 and lowering the emissions threshold of 25,000 tCO_{2e} for industrial facilities to include smaller emitters (Appendix C – Public Consultation Document).

Summarizing information from these engagements and from the interviews with professionals familiar with Singapore’s carbon tax policy, the following are the concerns and challenges of Carbon Tax implementation (NCCS, 2017, 2022; Fu, 2022; Ling, 2022):

1. **High Pass-On Effect and Impact on the Poor:** There is concern that the carbon tax could lead to a high pass-on effect, resulting in inflation. The worry is that this inflation would disproportionately affect low-income individuals.

On average, if the higher carbon tax is fully passed on to consumers, it could result in a \$4 increase in monthly utility bills for a four-room Housing Board flat. The National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) predicts that each \$5 increment in carbon tax might lead to a corresponding 1% rise in household electricity tariffs, potentially causing electricity bills to go up by approximately 4% in 2024 (Hong, 2023). To address this concern, the government will provide rebates to help alleviate some financial burdens. Singapore has allocated S\$300 worth of Climate vouchers to each of the 1.1 million HDB households under the Climate-Friendly Households Programme. These vouchers serve to offset the increased costs associated with energy-efficient and water-efficient appliances. (Fu, 2024).

2. **Carbon Leakage:** Another concern is carbon leakage. This refers to the possibility that businesses might relocate to countries with no or minimal carbon control measures, thus undermining the effectiveness of the tax. Minister Grace Fu addressed this during the debate on the Carbon Pricing Bill (Amendment Bill) that companies in the emission-intensive trade-exposed (EITE) sector, namely in the oil and gas, chemicals, manufacturing, and semiconductor sectors, will be provided allowances to help alleviate near-term competitiveness concerns as they work on low carbon and cleaner technologies (Qing and Begum, 2022).
3. **Competitiveness with Other Countries:** Singapore may face challenges competing with other countries that do not have stringent carbon control policies. The fear is that industries in Singapore could be at a disadvantage (Ling, 2022).
4. **Uncertainty Regarding Future Tax Increases:** Businesses and individuals are uncertain about how carbon tax rates might change in the future. This lack of predictability can create challenges for planning and investment decisions (Ling, 2022).
5. **Transparency in Determining Carbon Rates:** Stakeholders have voiced apprehension regarding the lack of transparency surrounding the determination of appropriate carbon tax rates. The methodology used to arrive at these rates is pivotal in fostering trust among various parties. Notably, during parliamentary debates aimed at increasing the carbon tax, the opposition has expressed reservations about the process employed to determine the appropriate rate adjustments. Ensuring transparency in this crucial aspect of environmental governance is essential for effective policy implementation and public confidence (Qing and Begum, 2022).

6. **Opacity in Allowances for high emitters in the emission-intensive trade-exposed (EITE) sector**, namely in the oil and gas, chemicals, manufacturing, and semiconductor sectors. There is a perceived lack of transparency regarding the allowances granted to high-intensity carbon emitters. This opacity raises questions about fairness and accountability (Qing and Begum, 2022).
7. **Representation in Consultation Processes:** In this study, two interviewees expressed concerns that participants in the consultation process sometimes feel their voices could be more adequately represented. They emphasized the need for the government to ensure inclusivity and consider diverse perspectives, which are essential for effective policymaking.

Performance of Carbon Pricing Implementation in Singapore

GHG Emissions

Singapore's per capita CO₂ emissions are relatively higher compared to many other countries. In the global ranking, Singapore's CO₂ emissions at 8.351 tCO₂/capita rank 21st out of 155 countries/territories for the year 2021 (IEA, 2023). While Singapore performs well in carbon intensity (CO₂ emissions per dollar of GDP), its high population density and economic activities contribute to a notable per capita emissions level. However, it is essential to consider Singapore's unique context and constraints as a densely built-up city-state with limited resources.

The official data from NCCS in 2021, puts GHG emissions at 53.7 MtCO₂e from about 50 facilities in the manufacturing, power, waste and water sectors. Globally this is only 0.1% of global GHG emissions (NCCS). This number is expected to continue to increase, however, the Singapore Green Plan 2030 aims is to peak at 60 MtCO₂e by 2030 and reduce to net-zero by 2050.

Figure 5. Singapore's Emissions Profile (NCCS, n.d.d).

The emissions profile above excludes estimated hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) emissions of around 4.0 MtCO₂e from the Refrigeration and Air-conditioning (RAC) sector in 2021. When more robust estimates are established, the national emissions profile will be updated in accordance with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) guidelines on continual improvement of national GHG inventories.

Carbon Tax Revenue and Expenditure

In terms of revenue from carbon tax, the Ministry of Finance reported S\$207.5 million were received in FY 2020, S\$197.9 million in FY 2021, S\$211.59 million in FY 2022, S\$200.197 million in FY 2023 and estimated 203.680 in 2024. Appendix D shows extracts of MOF Revenue and Expenditure Estimates for 2022 and 2024 (Ministry of Finance, 2022, 2024).

Figure 6. Carbon Tax Revenue.

As expressed in public forums and government announcements, revenue from carbon tax will be utilized to fund research, training, installation of energy and emissions monitoring equipment, and to alleviate operating expenditures during the transition. The following are examples of available grants:

1. Resource Efficiency Grant for Emissions (REG(E)). This grant supports manufacturing facilities and data centres in undertaking projects that improve their energy efficiency and other forms of eligible emissions reduction, to sustain competitiveness in a low-carbon future. The grant will be calculated based on the carbon abatement achieved by the project, capped at 50% of qualifying costs.
2. Energy Efficiency Fund (E2F) supports up to 70% of costs in Energy Efficient Technologies, including the identification of energy efficiency opportunities and monitoring energy consumption (Koo, 2022).

NEA has allocated more than S\$19.16 million for NEA's Energy Efficiency Fund (E2F) for energy efficient technologies projects and another S\$7.7 Million for Energy

Management Information System (EMIS), of which S\$587,750 and S\$494,368, respectively were actual expenditure up to end of Fiscal Year of 2022 (MOF 2024). Refer to Appendix D – Extract from Revenue and Expenditure Estimates for details.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

This case study on Singapore's carbon tax implementation examines the environmental governance aspects related to GHG reduction. The assessment uses a comprehensive list of attributes of environmental governance. It evaluates the effectiveness, equity, responsiveness, and robustness of Singapore's approach in implementing carbon tax to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions and meet its net-zero target by year 2050. The study considers three (3) key governance elements, namely, policies and regulations, organizational structure, and processes for negotiations and decision-making.

While positive attributes are identified, recommendations focus on enhancing fairness, justice and stakeholder participation as well as evaluating improvement in ecosystem functioning as evidence of an effective environmental governance.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this research is to review and evaluate the carbon reduction governance through carbon taxation in Singapore to determine whether it is effective, equitable, responsive, and robust in meeting the aims of UN SDG 13 on climate action, Singapore's commitment to Paris Agreement and in furtherance of Singapore Green Plan 2030. The study aims to answer the research question: Are the attributes and objectives of good governance present in the policies, structure, and processes for carbon pricing implementation in Singapore?

Specifically, the research goals are to:

1. Assess the attributes of CPA 2018, its subsequent amendments, and other relevant policies on the GHG emission reduction, whether these policies are effective, equitable, responsive, and robust;
2. Assess the attributes and interplay of formal structures such as the NCCS, IMCC, NEA and other ministries, non-governmental organizations namely industry associations, academe and expert individuals concerned with the implementation of CPA 2018;
3. Assess the attributes of policy making, negotiation and decision-making, ensuring transparency, just and fair distribution of socio-economic costs and benefits, inclusivity and accountability for results; and
4. Provide recommendations for improving environmental governance of carbon pricing and carbon tax implementation in Singapore.

V. RATIONALE

In line with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)'s call for urgent measures to battle climate change and its impacts, the Singapore government has pledged to achieve a net-zero target by 2050. Carbon Pricing emerges as a key strategy in curbing GHG emissions along with other measures under the Singapore Green Plan 2030, the country's most recent climate change strategy.

By assessing Singapore's carbon pricing journey, policymakers and stakeholders can identify areas for improvement, address potential obstacles, and enhance policy effectiveness. The governance review considers effectiveness, responsiveness, transparency, accountability, stakeholder engagement, and overall policy impact, shaping decisions and refining policies to achieve sustainability and mitigate climate change. These insights may also serve as a benchmark for other nations implementing similar carbon tax initiatives.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This study focuses exclusively on Carbon Tax as a component of carbon pricing scheme in Singapore. While both the Emission Trading System (ETS) and Carbon Tax contribute significantly to reducing greenhouse gases emissions, this investigation focusses specifically on the latter. It delves into the implementation of carbon tax in Singapore during from 2015 to 2023.

However, it is essential to acknowledge certain constraints. Time limitations hindered the ability to gather exhaustive data and conduct extensive interviews with experts and practitioners in the field of greenhouse gas reduction and carbon pricing. Government agencies, such as NCCS and NEA, responsible for implementation and coordination of carbon pricing, while they provide published data, they do not accept interviews, survey questionnaires, or requests for company names paying carbon taxes. Additionally, many interviewees chose anonymity, especially when their opinions could highlight implementation inadequacies or inefficiencies.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Country Profile of Singapore

The Republic of Singapore is a sovereign city-state and island country in Southeast Asia, situated at the tip of the Malay Peninsula. Singapore total land area, including offshore islands, is approximately 719.1 square kilometers (Singapore Land Authority, 2024). It comprises one main island, Singapore Island, and several other smaller islets. Characterized by its flat terrain with low-lying areas not exceeding 15 meters above sea level, Singapore's highest natural point stands at Bukit Timah Hill at 163.63 meters. Thirty per cent (30%) of Singapore's land lies below 5m above mean sea level making it vulnerable to effects of rising sea level predicted to rise by up to 1.15m by 2100, high tides and storm surge (Ting, 2024; CNA 2022). This relatively low-lying portion of the island is crucial to consider in terms of climate change adaptation and flood risk management.

Figure 7. Singapore topographic map.

Climate

The country is known for its consistent tropical rainforest climate with abundant rainfall, high and uniform temperatures, and high humidity all year round. Its climate is typified by two monsoon seasons separated by inter-monsoonal periods. The Northeast Monsoon occurs from December to March, and the Southwest Monsoon from June to September, making for no distinct dry or wet seasons. These conditions result in uniform temperature and pressure distribution, making Singapore prone to frequent cloudiness and showers. Extreme weather events, such as flash floods, have become more common due to the intense and non-discreet rainfall patterns influenced by climate change.

Singapore generally experiences low wind speeds which make it challenging to operate commercial wind turbines effectively (NCCS, n.d.e).

Demographics

The total population of Singapore as of 2023 is approximately 5.92 million people, of which 4.15 million are citizens and permanent residents. The population density is 8,058 people per square kilometer (third highest globally) with residents housed in high rise residential buildings.

Approximately 13.4% of the population are below 20 years old, 44.6% are working-age population of 20-64 years old, and 12.1% are 65 years and over (Department of Statistics Singapore, 2018).

Socioeconomic Profile

Singapore's economy exhibits significant diversification, drawing major contributions from finance, services, manufacturing, and trade. The nation boasts a

highly developed and successful free-market economy. With a per capita GDP of 82,807.6 USD in 2022, Singapore ranked tenth highest globally and first in the region according to World Bank's 2022 data. Due to its primarily urban population and limited physical space, Singapore encounters distinctive social, economic, and environmental challenges.

Construction and Development

Singapore's rapid urbanization and development have led to extensive land use for residential, commercial, and industrial purposes. The country employs innovative construction technologies and urban planning to maximize land use while attempting to balance green spaces within the urban infrastructure. Its forward-thinking approach to sustainable development includes initiatives such as green buildings, vertical gardens, and the integration of public transport systems to reduce reliance on private vehicles.

Administration & Land Use

The Singaporean government's stringent land-use policies aim to optimize the limited land area for various purposes – housing, industry, commerce, transportation, and recreation – in harmony with environmental conservation. The Urban Redevelopment Authority (URA) is responsible for urban planning, balancing economic growth and quality living space through long-term strategic land use and transportation planning (Urban Redevelopment Authority [URA], 2019).

Environmental Concerns and Climate Change

In the year 2021, Singapore's greenhouse gas emissions surged to 53.7 MtCO₂eq, representing an 8% increase compared to the previous year's total of 49.7 MtCO₂eq. This concerning trend underscores the critical need for robust policies aimed at curbing carbon emissions and adapting to the impacts of climate change. Without swift intervention, Singapore faces significant challenges in achieving its ambitious net-zero emissions target by 2050 (NCCS, 2021).

Enter the Green Plan 2030, a comprehensive national initiative. Also known as the Green Plan, it represents a whole-of-nation movement dedicated to advancing sustainable development within Singapore. This visionary roadmap outlines both ambitious and practical targets for the next decade. By aligning with the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda and the Paris Agreement, Singapore positions itself to realize its long-term aspiration: achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. The Green Plan is more than a policy - it is a commitment to a greener, more resilient future for Singapore and the planet (Ministry of Education et al., n.d.).

The key Targets of the Green Plan:

1. **Planting 1 million Trees:** The Green Plan aims to enhance Singapore's green cover by planting an additional one million trees. This initiative contributes to biodiversity, carbon sequestration, and overall environmental resilience.
2. **Quadrupling Solar Energy Deployment by 2025:** Singapore seeks to significantly expand its use of solar energy as it has serious difficulties in pursuing alternative energy options such as nuclear, hydroelectric, wind or geothermal power. By quadrupling solar energy deployment, the nation aims to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and promote cleaner energy sources.

3. Reducing Landfill Waste by 30% by 2030: The Green Plan emphasizes waste reduction and efficient waste management. By targeting a 30% reduction in waste sent to landfills, Singapore aims to minimize its environmental footprint.
4. Carbon-Neutral Schools: The plan sets a goal for at least 20% of schools in Singapore to become carbon neutral by 2030. This involves adopting sustainable practices, energy efficiency measures, and promoting environmental awareness among students.
5. Cleaner-Energy Cars: Starting from 2030, all newly registered cars in Singapore will be required to be cleaner-energy models. This move encourages the adoption of electric vehicles and reduces emissions from the transportation sector.

The Five Pillars of the Green Plan:

1. City in Nature: This pillar focuses on integrating nature into urban spaces, creating green corridors, enhancing biodiversity, and ensuring that Singapore remains a vibrant city in harmony with its natural environment.
2. Energy Reset: The Energy Reset pillar aims to transform Singapore's energy landscape by promoting clean and renewable energy sources, improving energy efficiency, and transitioning away from fossil fuels.
3. Sustainable Living: Encouraging sustainable lifestyles and responsible consumption is central to this pillar. It encompasses waste reduction, water conservation, and eco-friendly practices in daily life.
4. Green Economy: The Green Plan recognizes the economic opportunities associated with sustainability. It promotes green innovation, circular economy practices, and sustainable business models.

5. **Resilient Future:** This pillar addresses climate resilience, disaster preparedness, and adaptation strategies. It ensures that Singapore remains resilient in the face of climate change impacts.

Multi-Agency Effort: The Green Plan is a collaborative effort involving several ministries in Singapore. These include:

- **Ministry of Education:** Responsible for implementing sustainable practices in educational institutions.
- **Ministry of National Development:** Focuses on urban planning, green spaces, and sustainable infrastructure.
- **Ministry of Sustainability and the Environment:** Leads environmental policies, conservation efforts, and climate action.
- **Ministry of Trade and Industry:** Drives economic transformation toward sustainability.
- **Ministry of Transport:** Works on sustainable transportation solutions and reducing emissions from the transport sector.

The Green Plan underscores Singapore's commitment to address climate change and create a more sustainable future for its citizens and the planet. Carbon Pricing is a segment in the Singapore's overall Climate Change Strategy.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

Literature Review of Carbon Pricing Governance in Singapore

A literature review was conducted into the historical evolution, underlying rationale, and foundational principles of carbon pricing within the Singaporean context. The literature review was aimed to establish the necessary context for this environmental governance assessment of CPA 2018. Understanding the policy's intent, its overarching goals, the intricate process of policy formulation, consultation process, decision-making dynamics, and the requisite institutional structures for effective implementation—all contribute to a meaningful and informed evaluation of Singapore's carbon pricing policy.

The Assessment Tool

This case study of Singapore's carbon tax implementation under its carbon pricing policy, utilizes Bennett and Satterfield's framework on design and evaluation of environmental governance. (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018). This assessment framework was utilised by Falayi and colleagues (2021) in their study titled "A Scoping Review of Environmental Governance Challenges in Southern Africa from 2010 to 2020". Their findings revealed a multifaceted landscape of challenges related to natural resource management during the specified decade.

Bennett and Satterfield's (2018) environmental governance framework was selected for this study due to its comprehensive list of attributes and elements related to environmental governance. Unlike other analytical frameworks, such as adaptive governance (DeCaro et al., 2017) or topic-specific review of institutional interplay (Elsässer et al., 2021), Bennett and Satterfield's (2018) framework emphasizes four

key objectives; Effective, Equitable, Responsive and Robust Environmental Governance. Figure 8 depicts the Framework for understanding the objectives, attributes, and elements of environmental governance.

Bennett and Satterfield (2018) briefly describe each of the objectives of environmental governance in their framework as follows:

- a) **Effective environmental governance:** This objective underscores the importance of maintaining or enhancing the integrity and functioning of ecological and societal systems. Effective governance ensures that environmental systems thrive while meeting human needs.
- b) **Equitable Environmental Governance:** Engaging in multiple decision-making processes is crucial for producing socioeconomic outcomes that are inclusive, fair, just, and participatory. Equitable governance seeks to address disparities and promote social justice.
- c) **Responsive environmental governance:** Governance systems must be adaptable to changing socio-ecological conditions. Being responsive allows institutions to adjust and evolve as new challenges arise.
- d) **Robust Environmental Governance:** Robustness refers to institutions that persist, maintain performance, and effectively handle disruptions and crises. A resilient governance system ensures stability and continuity.

Figure 8. Framework for understanding the objectives, attributes, and elements of environmental governance (Bennett & Satterfield, 2018).

Interviews and Evaluation of Evidence

Based on their applicability to the context of Singapore, data from literature reviews and interviews were identified to form the basis for the assessment of each attribute. Interviews were conducted in semi-structured manner to allow for flexibility, and to gather more information and opinions from the experts (Pacardo et al., 2000). The experts included a research fellow from the academe, a member of industry association, a journalist, and select practitioners from manufacturing industry. Their diverse viewpoints enrich the understanding of Singapore’s carbon pricing journey

For example, in assessing the policy attribute under ‘Effective Institution’ the researcher gathered secondary data to substantiate whether carbon pricing policies

and laws contribute to maintaining the integrity and functionality of environmental governance. An assessment was done to determine whether the scope, goals, and aims of the CPA 2018 are well-defined, comprehensive, and effectively communicated to stakeholders. These factors informed the scoring process. Scoring followed a five-level Likert scale for quality measurement: that is, excellent=5, good=4, fair=3, poor=2, and very poor=1 (Step 6 in Figure 9). The steps were iterated when assessing the other two elements of environmental governance, namely, Structures and Processes.

Likert scale was selected for assessing attitudes, opinions, and perceptions on a subject being studied. It is a tool widely used for measuring attitudes, opinions and perceptions (Bhandari, 2023).

The highest score forms the final rating for the attribute. This score was presented to experts for confirmation. Where the scores vary significantly from the expert's initial response, discussions were conducted until agreement was achieved.

Appendix E contains attributes of environmental governance from Bennett and Satterfield's Environmental Governance Framework, and Appendix F, includes sample interview questions.

Figure 9. Research workflow.

IX. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Based on literature reviews and interviews, the Carbon Pricing Act of 2018 in Singapore has shown strong performance across several attributes of environmental governance. These attributes include Effective Direction, Effective Coordination, Capacity, Efficiency, Anticipatory measures, Legitimacy, and Flexibility. Specifically, these areas received an 'excellent' rating. While some attributes were rated as 'fair to poor,' many scored 'good.' The following paragraphs delve into the key evidence and basis for assessing each environmental governance objective.

Evidence of Effective Environmental Governance

According to Bennett and Satterfield (2018), effective environmental governance aims to maintain or enhance the functioning of environmental systems and ecosystem services by ensuring the persistence of species, habitats, and biodiversity. The key attributes of effective environmental governance include clear direction, coordination, capacity, informed decision-making, accountability, and efficiency. Achieving clear direction involves articulating precise vision, goals, and aims, as well as defining boundaries for actions and scope. These elements define what effective action entails and set milestones for achieving success. Ultimately, effective environmental governance is expected to lead to improved ecosystem functioning, greater biodiversity, increased productivity, and better environment health.

The review of Carbon Pricing Act (CPA) 2018 in Section 11.4 revealed that the design and implementation of this law show evidence of clear direction and well-

defined scope and goals. These definitions were articulated in various forums and public consultations (Section 11.7 and Appendix C of this report).

Carbon Pricing is part of the overarching Singapore Green Plan 2030. The scope of CPA includes direct carbon emissions from the manufacturing and manufacturing-related industry sector, as well as supply of electricity, gas, steam compressed air and chilled water for air condition, and water supply, sewage, and waste management. This covers about 50 facilities and the majority (80%) of GHG gases in Singapore as reported on the NCCS website (NCCS, n.d.d).

The CPA contains a listing of the types of greenhouse gases directly emitted from these industries. Having these GHG listed in the main legislation deters unplanned and careless application of the act which may result to confusion among affected emitters and inaccurate emissions reports. Appendix A is an extract of the GHG subject to CPA 2018.

The initial carbon tax rate was set at S\$5/tCO_{2e} for the first five years from 2019 to 2023 to allow a transition period for companies emitting GHG to adjust. Cognizant that this rate is one of the lowest amongst jurisdictions implementing carbon tax, and may be too low to effect any change, the carbon tax rate was increased to S\$25/tCO_{2e} for the years 2024-2025 and S\$45/tCO_{2e} by 2026 to 2027 and targeted to increase to S\$50/tCO_{2e} up to S\$80/tCO_{2e} by 2030 (NCCS, n.d.a). Public consultation on tax rate was conducted in 2022 before amendments were made. Refer to Appendix C for information on results of one of the public consultations held before increasing the carbon tax.

Figure 10. Singapore tax rate increases.

Notably, the leap from S\$5 to S\$25, 5x over a period of 5 years is steeper than British Columbia's leap from \$10 to \$30 or 3x over a period of 4 years, hailed as the most successful CT implementation. Refer to Section II.3 - Experiences in other Countries. The rationale for this increase was presented during the deliberation of the amendment bill (Fu, 2022).

The Minister for Environment and Sustainability also hinted during the debate in November 2022, that carbon tax will be between S\$50 to S\$80 by 2030. This provides companies with some level of certainty needed to strategize and implement effective carbon reduction measures. Simultaneously, households can make informed decisions to curtail their electricity consumption. The Minister also emphasized that the revenue generated from carbon taxes is allocated to bolster decarbonization initiatives, facilitate the shift toward a sustainable green economy, and mitigate the effects on both businesses and households (Fu, 2022).

Efficiency is also demonstrated in the processes undertaken to implement CPA 2018. From Table 2 in Section II.6.1 Legislative history of Carbon Pricing Act, it is evident that the process from bill presentation to approval was remarkably swift,

spanning only 40 calendar days (equivalent to 28 working days). Even more impressive was the speed at which subsequent amendments were handled—taking just over a month to be debated and approved. This expedited deliberation period owes its success to proactive public consultations and an extensive awareness campaign. Notably also, these efforts extended beyond mere carbon pricing discussions, encompassing the broader climate change strategy.

Coordination among state agencies and non-governmental organizations, youth groups, private sector, and the general public is evident in Singapore. This is reiterated in the slogan ‘whole-of-nation’ approach described in Section VII.2 Environmental Concerns and Climate Change and Section II.5 Structural Arrangement to implement the Carbon Pricing Policy. The roles, functions, and mandates of different government agencies and members of the IMCC are defined to ensure clear boundaries and accountability for results. NCCS, as the coordinating body for all climate change matters, ensures all parties work together towards a common goal.

Accountable attribute is also evident in the results of performance audits conducted by the Office of the Auditor-General on the Ministry of Sustainability and Environment wherein no findings were raised for FY 2021-22 and FY 2022/23 (Attorney-General’s Office Singapore, 2023).

Capacity building is evident through various research and development studies, as well as education and training programs for industry personnel, including Energy Managers and GHG verifiers. Additionally, resources are made available to enhance energy efficiency as discussed in Section 11.9.2 – Carbon Tax Revenue and Expenditure. Energy managers who participated in this study reported substantial support from the National Environment Agency (NEA). The NEA provided training and coaching to companies, assigning dedicated NEA

representatives to serve as the main point of contact. This NEA representative regularly communicates with and advises companies on policy changes, as well as corrections and improvements to their monitoring plans and emissions reports.

While capacity and capability have been strengthened, the realization of improved ecosystem services due to effective governance understandably remains a long-term goal. Given that Singapore’s greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are still significantly distant from its net-zero targets and account for only 0.1% of global emissions, these outcomes are expected to materialize over time.

Using the above data and information, Figure 11 shows the rating on a 5-level Likert Scale for each of the attributes of effective governance.

Figure 11. Effective governance rating.

Evidence of Equitable Environmental Governance

Bennett and Satterfield (2018) emphasized that socially equitable environmental governance requires active participation, recognition of diverse perspectives, and fair distribution of benefits and responsibilities. Stakeholders, including marginalized or vulnerable groups (such as low-income families, small and medium scale enterprises,

and very high fossil-based power generators and users), must actively participate in shaping environmental policies. Inclusion ensures that all voices contribute to well-informed and holistic decision-making.

Upon evaluating government consultation, announcements, and their responses to feedback and suggestions, it becomes clear that the Singapore government strives for social equity and inclusivity. These were evident in public forum as early as 2012 when the Energy Conservation Act was passed, in 2015 when the government presented Singapore's plans to address climate change and during parliamentary debates in 2018 when the CPA was first introduced and in 2022 when CPA was amended to increase the price of carbon emission. There is evidence of recognition of burdens associated with carbon tax implementation and addressing these burdens, i.e., allowing staggered increases of carbon tax, allowances and subsidies. These are discussed in Section II.7(Debates and Consultation) and Section II.8 (Key Changes to CPA 2018) of this report.

Despite Singapore's active engagement and the government's responses to concerns, certain issues persist regarding the transparency of carbon tax implementation as discussed in Section II.8.1. Specifically, the establishment of rates and the allowances granted to high greenhouse gas emitters during the transition to net-zero emissions remain points of contention. These concerns highlighted the absence of a clear mechanism to ensure equitable distribution of socio-economic costs and benefits. There appears to be no explicit framework guaranteeing that different groups receive a balanced share of costs and benefits.

Furthermore, an issue surfaces during the interviews with experts concerning what appears to be lack of diverse representation among stakeholders engaged in public consultations. While consultation reports do exist, details about the scope and

inclusivity of these consultations remain unavailable. It is plausible that the same respondents represent only a minority of the affected population.

Regarding access to justice, the Ministry of Law has established the Public Defender Office (PDO) in 2022 to assist with criminal cases (Ministry of Law Singapore, 2022). However, it remains uncertain whether this service will be extended to civil rights cases. Additionally, due to the lack of an explicit constitutional provision regarding the right to a clean and healthy environment, achieving access to justice on behalf of the ecosystem may take time.

Considering the foregoing evidence, the assessment showed lower rating on 'Participation', 'Fair', and 'Just' governance. Refer to Figure 12 for the rating.

Figure 12. Equitable governance rating.

Notably, this rating is consistent with World Bank’s Worldwide Governance Indicator for ‘Voice and Accountability’ which falls in the 50-60% range, where 90-100% is desirable (World Bank Group, n.d.).

Evidence of Responsive Environment Governance

According to Bennett and Satterfield (2018), responsive environmental governance aims to create adaptable systems that can effectively respond to changing environmental and social conditions across diverse contexts. These governance arrangements embody several key principles such as learning and adaptation through continuous monitoring, evaluation and communication, knowledge sharing and collaboration, anticipation, and preparedness through consideration and analyses of both long-term and short-term consequences, and adaptive governance processes that allows spaces for dialogues, reflection and deliberation for revisiting policies and management actions.

This assessment showed that Singaporean government adapted lessons from other jurisdictions when designing its carbon pricing policy. Section 11.3 of this report

contains a summary of significant experiences from selected countries, particularly implementation experiences in British Columbia, Canada and South Korea for carbon tax rate and setting the second emissions threshold of 25,000 MtCO₂e as tax-liable emissions, respectively.

Furthermore, Singapore demonstrates remarkable foresight across various aspects of governance, extending beyond carbon pricing. Section II.8 of this report highlighted that changes to the CPA 2018 were crucial in anticipation of external pressures such as European Union's decision to impose CO₂ emissions costs on specific imports (including steel, cement, fertilizers, aluminium, and electricity) starting in 2026 and an opportunity for Singapore in the research and development of low carbon technologies, Carbon Utilisation and Storage (CCUs). This proactive approach fosters green growth opportunities both within Singapore and globally, aligning with the world's transition toward resource-efficient and sustainable practices.

In addition to the increased carbon tax rate, the amendment to the CPA, also included the setting up the International Carbon Credits framework or ICC framework for reductions outside of Singapore, capped at 5% of taxable emissions. This allows carbon tax-liable companies options to reduce their carbon tax liabilities. These are evidence of an innovative and adaptive governance.

In this context, the attributes of responsive environmental governance are impressively evident and garnered high scores. Figure 13 shows the ratings.

Figure 13. Responsive governance rating.

Evidence of Robust Environmental Governance

The aim of environmental governance is to establish robust institutions that endure over time, sustain their performance, and withstand disruptions and crises. Such institutions are characterized by their legitimacy, interconnectedness, nested structure, and polycentricity. Legitimate institutions are driven by a shared vision, endowed with formal legitimacy through laws or policies, and recognized as legitimate by their constituents and stakeholders, ensuring solid political justification and community backing (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018).

Singapore Green Plan 2030 and other climate actions dovetail from formal policies on energy and climate action laws. Section 11.4.3 of this report describes such laws consistent and nested with CPA to strengthen and ensure success of climate action strategies.

Robust networks of institutions are interconnected both horizontally and vertically, often through the facilitation of bridging organization such as the NCCS.

These networks enable collaboration, the exchange of knowledge and information, and the spread of innovations (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018). These attributes are demonstrated in the governance structures defined in Section II.5 and Appendix G for private sector support.

Legitimacy is crucial in generating quality emissions reports. Verified emissions data substantiate the accuracy and credibility of information in the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) 2030, reports to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), publications in government websites, and information provided to the media. Refer to Section II.4.1 on Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV), Section II.8.1 on NCCS CO₂ emissions profile, and the Ministry of Finance's data on revenue, expenditure, and performance indicator in Section II.8.2 as examples of reports that need accurate data and information.

Finally, regular review and amendment of relevant legislations ensure that laws are up-to-date and science-based. For example, the inclusion of Nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) in the amended list of GHG emission as reckonable GHG could negatively impact the electronics industry, one of the major industries in Singapore. However, the move showcased Singapore's adherence to science and sincere efforts to address the reduction of GHG.

These pieces of evidence contribute to high scores for Legitimate governance. Refer to Figure 14.

Figure 14. Robust governance rating.

Final Rating

The final rating for each attribute was determined by selecting the highest scores from the five-level Likert scale for each of the attributes. Table 3 is a list of the final rating on environmental governance of Carbon Pricing in Singapore.

Table 3

Summary of Environmental Governance Evaluation Rating

Objectives	Attributes	Rating
Effective Environmental Governance	Direction	Good
	Coordination	Good
	Capacity	Good
	Informed	Fair
	Accountable	Fair
Equitable Environmental Governance	Efficient	Good
	Recognition	Fair
	Participation	Good
	Fair	Fair
	Just	Fair
	Learning	Fair

Objectives	Attributes	Rating
Responsive Environmental Governance	Anticipatory	Good
	Adaptive	Good
	Innovative	Good
	Flexible	Excellent
Robust Environmental Governance	Legitimate	Excellent
	Connected	Fair
	Nested	Good
	Polycentric	Good

Verification and Comparison of Results with other Governance Indicators

The assessment results from this study were submitted to the National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) for comments and verification. However, NCCS responded that the agency does not endorse individual research papers.

To bolster confidence in the study's findings, the researcher compared the results with established governance assessments. Specifically, the researcher references the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) from the World Bank and the Rule of Law Index from the World Justice Project. These indices are widely used by various countries, including the Philippines, to evaluate governance performance and administration of law (National Economic and Development Authority, n.d.).

WGI uses six governance indicators: Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence Program, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption. Of these six (6), Voice and Accountability is rated low at below 50%, where 100% is the highest. Voice and Accountability represent the level of public participation, openness and transparency of government decision-making and actions.

Figure 15. Worldwide Governance Index results for Singapore.

Source: Worldwide Governance Indicators (www.govindicators.org)

Another source of information to compare the results of this study is from World Justice Project (n.d.). There are eight (8) factors considered under the Rule of Law. Singapore’s scores are shown in Figure 16. Note that the higher the number or 1.0 or 100% is the strongest, 0.0 is the weakest.

Figure 16. Rule of Law Index - Singapore.

Notably, ‘Open Government’ is weak in Singapore, scoring 0.61 out of a maximum of 1.0 or 100%. WJP’s definition of ‘Open Government’ is as follows:

“Open Government

Factor 3 of the WJP Rule of Law Index measures the openness of government defined by the extent to which a government shares information, empowers people with tools to hold the government accountable, and fosters

citizen participation in public policy deliberations. This factor measures whether basic laws and information on legal rights are publicized and evaluates the quality of information published by the government.”

Figure 17 shows sub-factors under ‘Open Government’. Of these, the factors on Right to Information at 0.52, Complaint Mechanisms at 0.62, and Civic Participation at 0.51 out of 1.0 are considered low (World Justice Project Report, n.d.). This finding is likewise consistent with the results of this study on the environmental governance of Carbon Pricing in Singapore.

Figure 17. Sub factors of ‘Open Government’.

X. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on assessment and evaluation results, there is substantial evidence that the environmental governance of the Singapore Carbon Pricing Act 2018 is effective, equitable, resilient, and robust. It not only addresses immediate concerns but also paves the way for achieving the country's commitment to the Paris Agreement's net-zero CO₂ emissions target by 2050. It lays the foundation for a sustainable and environmentally conscious future.

However, this study has also highlighted areas for improvement. The following are the recommendations.

1. **Enhance Design and Implementation of Carbon Pricing (CPA 2018):**

- *Transparency and Participation:* To enhance transparency and foster participation, it is essential to disclose comprehensive details regarding discussions with high-emitting companies or those receiving government allowances. This information should encompass the type and extent of their support, as well their progress or contributions toward achieving net-zero emissions commitments. Such transparency can mitigate concerns and suspicions of favoritism by the authorities.
- *Fair Distribution of Costs and Benefits:* Develop and make known policies and mechanisms to ensure that socio-economic costs and benefits are distributed fairly. This will ensure that various groups receive an equitable balance of costs and benefits.
- *Improve Access to Data and Information:* Ensuring transparency in carbon pricing policies is crucial for building trust among stakeholders and promoting effective environmental governance. To achieve this, it is crucial

to provide regular updates on the performance metrics and key performance indicators related to carbon tax revenue, expenditures for carbon mitigation initiatives, key programs, and beneficiaries of subsidies. Making this information accessible and comprehensible to the public, perhaps through the National Climate Change Secretariat (NCCS) website, can enhance public awareness and engagement.

2. **Conduct environmental governance assessment** using Bennett and Satterfield's environmental governance framework.
 - It is recommended that the Singapore government and other jurisdictions conduct an objective self-assessment of their environmental governance.
 - To ensure a more inclusive public participation, conduct surveys on a representative sample of affected companies (high emitters and SMEs), households, and environmental groups to assess the socio-economic impact of Carbon Pricing. A sample set of questions is included in Appendix H-Sample Questionnaire for High GHG Emitters, SMEs and General Public.
3. **Measure the overall ecosystem performance** by conducting comprehensive studies measuring improvement or changes in ecosystem functions. Every 5-10 years, conduct spatio-temporal analysis on changes in land use land cover and its impacts, changes in land surface temperature, biodiversity assessment, and overall environmental health, and correlate results against the goals of carbon pricing and the Singapore Green Plan 2030. The results of these studies should be comprehensible and accessible to the public.

By addressing these concerns, Singapore can further enhance the effectiveness of its carbon pricing mechanisms and promote a fair and transparent transition toward a low-carbon economy.

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Appendices

Appendix A

List of GHG covered in CPA 2018 (National Environment Agency, n.d.a)

Covered under the Carbon Pricing Act		Emissions excluded from the Carbon Pricing Act
Reckonable emissions	Non-reckonable emissions	
<p>All direct emissions of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, NF₃, HFCs and PFCs, from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel combustion • Industrial processes and product use (IPPU), <p>excluding emissions defined as non-reckonable.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> Reckonable emissions also include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CH₄ and N₂O emissions from combustion of biofuels or biomass. • CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from combustion of diesel with sulphur content of more than 10ppm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SF₆ emitted in the course of manufacturing, installing, using or disposing of any electrical equipment • CO₂ emissions used and emitted in the course of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ purging, ○ blasting, ○ using any lubricant or paraffin wax, ○ combustion of any of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ biodiesels ▪ biogasoline ▪ charcoal ▪ landfill gas ▪ sludge gas ▪ sulphite lyes (black liquor) ▪ wood or wood waste ▪ other biogas ▪ other liquid biofuel ▪ other primary solid biomass • HFCs and PFCs emitted in the course of using any refrigeration and air-conditioning equipment for non-manufacturing purposes • HFCs and PFCs listed in Table 2.1 • Any GHG emitted in the course of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ using any fire protection equipment, ○ using any fuel on which excise duty is payable, or which is exempt from the payment of excise duty, under the Customs Act (Cap. 70), and ○ emitted as a fugitive emission (excluding flaring and venting). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirect emissions (Scope 2 and Scope 3) e.g. from electricity consumption • Emissions from land-based activities (as defined by the UNFCCC) • Transport emissions

Appendix B

Monitoring and Reporting Spreadsheets (Attorney-General's Chambers of Singapore, n.d.)

National Environment Agency (NEA's) MRV regulations, Worksheet for Fuel Combustion. This worksheet is available at NEA website. Accessible online to companies required to prepare emissions report. Below is the main page (Total Reckonable GHG Emissions) and next page is the worksheet for Fuel Combustion. Training is given to users of the spreadsheet.

NOTES:

- 1) Default conversion factors provided in this template are aligned with the Measurement and Reporting Guidelines developed by the National Environment Agency (NEA)
- 2) For reporting period 2019 to reporting period 2023, the Global Warming Potentials of GHGs are based on the First Schedule of the Carbon Pricing Act. Pls refer to the regulation for more details. [here](#)
- 3) From reporting period 2024 onwards, please refer to SN39 of CP(Amendment) Bill for more details on the GWPs of the GHGs. [here](#)
- 4) Please note that the conversion factors in this calculator are aligned with 2006 IPCC Guideline.
- 5) Please note that only reckonable GHG emissions contributes towards the emission threshold. For details on non-reckonable GHG emissions, please refer to Part 2 of the Second Schedule of the Carbon Pricing Act. [here](#)

The following emissions thresholds are stated under Part 1 of the Second Schedule of the Carbon Pricing Act.

First Emissions Threshold (Reportable)	2,000	tonne CO ₂ e of Reckonable GHG emissions
Second Emissions Threshold (Taxable)	25,000	tonne CO ₂ e of Reckonable GHG emissions

TOTAL RECKONABLE GHG EMISSIONS

Fuel Combustion (FC)	0.00	tonne CO ₂ e
Industrial Processes and Product Use (IPPU)	0.00	tonne CO ₂ e
TOTAL (FC + IPPU)	0.00	tonne CO₂e

The cells within this template are colour-coded to allow users to identify their functions according to the legend below.

User input	A light green cell(s) to input text information or numeric data.
default conversion factors	A blue cell(s) containing default conversion factors (net calorific values and emission factors).
calculated based on cell formula	A light red cell(s) containing intermediate calculations based on the cell formula provided.
non-reckonable	A grey cell(s) to indicate non-reckonable emission and emission factors.
Total or sub-total	A yellow cell(s) to indicate total or sub-total GHG emissions.
	A black cell(s) to indicate a non-applicable field.

Version 2. Last updated on 30 Nov 2023

Disclaimer		Total Reckonable GHG Emissions		1. Fuel Combustion (FC)		2. Ethylene Production		3. Ethylene oxide production		4. Flares		5. Vents		7. Coal Gasification		8. IC and Semicon Production		
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O				
<p>1) Should quantities of fuel combusted be available in energy units of GigaJoules, please fill in the figure in Column C (in GJ) based on the Net Calorific Value (NCV).</p> <p>2) The conversion from Gross Calorific Value (GCV) to NCV for Energy units are: Solid & Liquid Fuels = Quantity (GJ) in GCV x 0.95. Gaseous Fuels = Quantity (GJ) in GCV x 0.9</p> <p>3) The conversion from Gross Calorific Value (GCV) to NCV for Energy units are: Solid & Liquid Fuels = Quantity (GJ) in GCV x 0.95. Gaseous Fuels = Quantity (GJ) in GCV x 0.9</p> <p>4) With respect to Regulation 6(4)(c) of the Carbon Pricing (Measurement, Reporting and Verification) Regulations, you are encouraged to use site-specific conversion factors (i.e. net calorific value, emission factor) wherever possible. Should site-specific conversion factors be available, please overwrite the default factors originally provided in the relevant cells. Kindly note that all cells below can be overwritten.</p> <p>5) Emissions (and emission factors) for non-reckonable GHGs (CO₂ from biogenic fuels and CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O from diesel) have been greyed out accordingly, and excluded from the total summation in Row 13 and Column J highlighted in yellow below.</p> <p>6) The following Global Warming Potentials² (GWP) are imbedded in the formula of Column J in the table below: 1 for CO₂, 28 for CH₄ and 265 for N₂O.</p>																		
		Energy Consumption			CO ₂		CH ₄		N ₂ O		TOTAL							
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J							
		Consumption (Annual Quantity)	Net Calorific Value	Consumption [C=AxB]	CO ₂ Emission Factor	CO ₂ Emissions [E=C*D/1000]	CH ₄ Emission Factor	CH ₄ Emissions [G=C*F/1000]	N ₂ O Emission Factor	N ₂ O Emissions [I=C*H/1000]	Actual CO ₂ -Equivalent Emissions							
		(GJ/Unit)	(GJ/Unit)	(GJ)	(kg CO ₂ / GJ)	(tonne CO ₂)	(kg CH ₄ / GJ)	(tonne CH ₄)	(kg N ₂ O / GJ)	(tonne N ₂ O)	(tonne CO ₂ e)							
		Unit																
TOTAL RECKONABLE EMISSIONS FROM FUEL COMBUSTION																		
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
	Anthracite	tonne	26.70	0.000	96.30	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0015	0.000	0.000							
	Aviation Gasoline	tonne	44.30	0.000	79.00	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Biodiesel (non-reckonable CO ₂)	tonne	27.00	0.000	79.00	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Bio gasoline (non-reckonable CO ₂)	tonne	27.00	0.000	79.00	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Bitumen	tonne	40.20	0.000	80.70	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Steel Furnace Gas	tonne	2.47	0.000	280.00	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0051	0.000	0.000							
	Brown Coal Biquasas	tonne	30.70	0.000	97.95	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0015	0.000	0.000							
	Charcoal (non-reckonable CO ₂)	tonne	29.50	0.000	112.00	0.000	0.200	0.000	0.0040	0.000	0.000							
	Coal Tar	tonne	28.00	0.000	80.70	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0015	0.000	0.000							
	Coke Oven Coke / Lignite Coke	tonne	28.20	0.000	107.00	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0015	0.000	0.000							
	Coke Oven Gas	tonne	38.70	0.000	44.40	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0051	0.000	0.000							
	Coking Coal	tonne	28.20	0.000	94.60	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0015	0.000	0.000							
	Crude Oil	tonne	42.30	0.000	73.30	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Ethane	tonne	46.40	0.000	67.60	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0051	0.000	0.000							
	Gas Coke	tonne	28.20	0.000	107.00	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.0051	0.000	0.000							
	Gas / Diesel Oil (non-reckonable CO ₂ , CH ₄ and N ₂ O)	tonne	43.00	0.000	74.10	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Gas / Diesel Oil (high sulphur) ²	tonne	43.00	0.000	74.10	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.0060	0.000	0.000							
	Industrial Waste ²	tonne	10.00	0.000	143.00	0.000	0.030	0.000	0.0040	0.000	0.000							

Appendix C

Public Consultation in Oct 2022

A summary of the Oct 2022 Feedback Received from REACH Public Consultation on Singapore's Raised Climate Ambition (NCCS, 2022)

On behalf of NCCS, REACH conducted a public consultation on Singapore's Raised Climate Ambition from 5 to 26, September 2022. Four hundred ninety (490) respondents participated in the consultation from various sectors. NCCS indicated that prior to this public consultation, REACH and NCCS had reached out to 1,200 stakeholders including youth and business representatives, NGOs and the academe.

The majority of the respondents were between 20-39. Refer to the graph below.

Figure 1A. Demographics of respondents

On the question about the intention to achieve net zero emissions by 2050, 66% of the respondents said that the target was 'not sufficiently ambitious', with 126 of them suggesting to target between 2040 and 2049.

Regarding enhancing the 2030 NDC, 62% of 302 respondents agreed that the NDC should be enhanced and most of the respondents (94%) indicated their willingness to make sacrifices to help achieve the net-zero ambitions.

While there may be trade-offs or inconveniences, I am willing to contribute / play my part in helping Singapore realise its net-zero ambition.

■ Strongly Agree ■ Agree ■ Neutral ■ Disagree ■ Strongly Disagree

The respondents also suggested the following:

1. Diversify and pivot away from emissions-intensive industries by setting targets for different sectors and increase output of more sustainable products.
2. Implementation of decarbonization plans in all industry sectors and for the government to increase grants and subsidies particularly for SMEs in their transition to green operations.

3. Widening the mandatory emissions reporting to include not only scope 1 but also scope 2 and 3 using verifiable emissions report and avoid greenwashing.
4. Divest away from fossil-based fuels and increase funding and investments for non-fossil-based projects and other clean energy projects.
5. Conduct more research and development in new green technologies.
6. Import clean electricity and support efforts to develop the ASEAN power grid.
7. Purchase carbon credits as a last resort.
8. Encourage green practices such as nature-based solutions, preserve natural ecosystems, support green transport and use of electric vehicles.
9. Expand projects for green infrastructure, and mandate green building designs.
10. Support individual efforts in reducing GHG, such reducing meat consumption, use of public transport, reduce consumption of water and electricity and reduce food waste, support local agriculture.
11. Continue conversation and consultation with the public on climate action issues.
12. Cushion the impacts of climate actions on the poor. Provide subsidies.
13. Review and recalibrate the carbon tax policy, with possible reduction of emissions thresholds.

Appendix D

Extract from Revenue and Expenditures Estimates from Ministry of Finance (Ministry of Finance, 2022, 2024)

Below are extracts from the Ministry of Finance Revenue and Expenditures Reports for year 2022 and 2024. Carbon Tax is Account Code 8331. For 2023 to 2024, there has been an increase of 1.7% in revenue from Carbon Tax.

TOTAL ESTIMATED RECEIPTS FOR FY2022 BY OBJECT CLASS

Account Code	Revenue Item	Actual FY2020	Estimated FY2021	Revised FY2021	Estimated FY2022	Change Over FY2021	
		\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	%
B00	TAX REVENUE	61,408,452,028	69,963,968,000	72,797,822,000	73,709,037,000	911,215,000	1.3
B331	Carbon Tax	207,529,760	191,290,000	197,914,000	197,914,000	0	0.0

TOTAL ESTIMATED RECEIPTS FOR FY2024 BY OBJECT CLASS

Account Code	Revenue Item	Actual FY2022	Estimated FY2023	Revised FY2023	Estimated FY2024	Change Over FY2023	
		\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	%
B00	TAX REVENUE	82,707,574,367	88,288,593,000	94,959,626,000	99,031,080,000	4,071,454,000	4.3
B33	CARBON TAX	211,593,060	215,233,000	200,197,000	203,680,000	3,483,000	1.7
B331	Carbon Tax	211,593,060	215,233,000	200,197,000	203,680,000	3,483,000	1.7

In terms of budget and expenditures, a total of S\$26,864,700.00 (19,164,700.00 +7,700,000.00) has been allotted for NEA programmes on Energy Efficient Technologies and Energy Management information Systems (EMIS). Of that amount, around S\$2,581,418.00 (415,841 +171,909 +499,300+494,368+1,000,000) have been disbursed since year 2021, 2022, and 2023 for these two projects.

Project Title	Total Project Cost	Actual Expenditure Up to end of FY2021	Actual FY2022	Estimated FY2023	Revised FY2023	Estimated FY2024
National Environment Agency Programme						
New Projects	---	---	0	6,120,800	135,000	1,118,100
Energy Efficiency Fund (E2F) – Energy Efficient Technologies	19,164,700	415,841	171,909	499,300	377,700	779,600
Energy Efficiency Fund (E2F) - Energy Management Information System (EMIS)	7,700,000	0	494,368	1,000,000	877,700	809,800

KPIs (Key performance indicators) were also included in the Budget 2024. The list of indicators are for Ministry of Sustainability and Environment. Specifically, for Climate Change resilience and transition to a low-carbon future, the KPI for year 2021 is 53.7 MtCO_{2e} Total GHG. As indicated in the annotation, the actual amount in FY2022 will only be available in year 2024 due to lag time of submitted data to NEA.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Desired Outcomes

- A liveable and endearing home
- A smart, resilient and sustainable water system
- Food safety and security achieved sustainably
- A zero waste nation and circular economy
- Climate change resilience and transition to a low-carbon future
- Advancement of Singapore's strategic and economic interests relating to the environment, water and food

Key Performance Indicators

Desired Outcome	Performance Indicator ¹	Actual FY2021	Actual FY2022	Revised FY2023 ²	Estimated FY2024 ³
Climate change resilience and transition to a low-carbon future	Total Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions (million tonnes of CO ₂ -equivalent; MtCO ₂ e) ⁴	53.7	NA ¹⁰	NA ¹¹	NA

¹ All data are reported on calendar year basis.

² Data for "Revised FY2023" column refers to projected figures for 2023.

³ Data for "Estimated FY2024" column refers to targets for 2024.

⁴ Pollution incidents only include substantiated air pollution cases which have significant impacts on the environment and/or public health.

⁵ Pollution incidents refer to substantiated water pollution cases which have resulted in significant water pollution in open drains and/or waterways.

⁶ Nowcast is a short-term forecast of 2 hours. Weather systems in the tropics are dynamic in nature and can develop and dissipate within a short span of time, typically around an hour.

⁷ The 4 food items are Seafood, Chicken, Pork and Vegetables for 2021. The 3 food items are Seafood, Pork and Vegetables for 2022. The 4 food items are Seafood, Eggs, Pork and Vegetables for 2023.

⁸ An outbreak is defined as ≥15 people affected by food poisoning incidents that have triggered One Health joint investigations.

⁹ The GHG inventory is refined regularly, in accordance with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Good Practice Guidance.

¹⁰ Data will be available only in 2024, due to the lag time for external organisations/agencies to submit their data to NEA.

¹¹ Target to reduce Total GHG emissions to 60MtCO₂e in 2030 after peaking earlier.

Appendix E

Environmental Governance Attributes (Bennett and Satterfield, 2018). Definitions of

Attributes in terms of Qualities or Capacities of governance

The following list of environmental governance objectives and attributes is lifted from Bennett and Satterfield’s framework. Rather than interpreting these attributes further, the definitions serve as foundation for collecting data and evidence of their presence and adequate demonstration in the environmental governance in Singapore. Collection of evidence was done via literature reviews and interviews.

A. Effective environmental governance (direction, coordination, capacity, informed, accountable, efficient)

Attributes (Qualities or Capacities)	General Characteristics or Inputs (Capacity)	Idealized Outputs (Functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (Performance)
Direction	Scope, goals and aims are comprehensive, clearly articulated and communicated to stakeholders. Clear boundaries on action and scope exist.	Defines what effective action encompasses and sets milestones for achieving success.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in ecosystem functioning. • Greater biodiversity or species. • Increases in productivity of system or provisioning of ecosystem services. • Better environmental health.
Coordination	The roles, functions, and mandates of different governments, agencies and organizations are coordinated. A coordinating body or unit is present.	Produces system of rules for use, mechanisms for exclusion, management actions and spatial coverage that are complementary and adequate to achieve objectives. Provides a forum for discussion, debate, negotiating and resolving trade-offs.	
Capacity	Capacity, skills and resources are sufficient and are being actively developed. Capable and visionary leadership is present. Mechanisms are present to resolve conflicts between groups.	Enables successful decision-making and the initiation, organization, implementation and evaluation of actions.	

Informed	Planning and management decisions and actions are informed by best available information and integration of a diversity of knowledge types and systems.	Increases the likelihood that management actions will lead to effective outcomes.
Accountable	Procedures are present to hold governors accountable for performance of system. Mechanisms are in place to ensure that means and rationales for making decisions are transparent.	Ensures that governors act on mandated decisions and that effective actions are being taken.
Efficient	Efficacy guides decisions regarding management actions and deployment of resources. Time requirements of actors are reasonable. Economic costs and actions taken are commensurate with productivity of system.	Maximizes the productivity of management actions while minimizing the wasteful use of available resources.

B. Equitable environmental governance (recognition, participation, fair, just)

Attributes (Qualities or Capacities)	General Characteristics or Inputs (Capacity)	Idealized Outputs (Functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (Performance)
Recognition	Policies and processes ensure acknowledgement of, respect for and incorporation of diverse perspectives, values, cultures and rights. Views of marginalized and vulnerable groups are considered.	Facilitates socially acceptable governance and perceptions of legitimacy. Aids in the design of management actions that are appropriate to the social context.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion in decision-making processes. • Improved socio-economic outcomes. • Increases in quality of life or wellbeing. • More fair distribution of wealth. • Better access to justice and protection of rights.
Participation	Spaces and processes to enable participation and collective choice are present. Structures that ensure the representation and engagement of different stakeholder groups are in place.	Contributes to just power relations and decision-making processes. Leads to plans and actions that represent the interests of different groups. Allows parties to democratically debate decisions and maintain dignity.	

Fair	Mechanisms are in place to ensure socio-economic costs and benefits are just and fairly distributed. Rights and responsibilities are shared and assigned fairly. Unequal circumstances are considered.	Ensures a fair balance of costs and benefits accrue to different groups.
Just	Laws and policies are present to protect local rights and mechanisms ensure that groups have access to justice.	Ensures rights (e.g., title, historical tenure, access, use, management) are not undermined and that reparations or compensation are made for past damages.

C. Responsive governance – Learning, Anticipatory, Adaptive, Innovative, Flexible

Attributes (Qualities or Capacities)	General Characteristics or Inputs (Capacity)	Idealized Outputs (Functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (Performance)
Learning	Monitoring, evaluation, reflections and communication of performance is institutionalized. Processes and platforms are in place to co-produce knowledge and enhance social and institutional memory.	Ensures that information is produced, documented, shared and informs decision-making.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables the resilience of resource. • Enables the resilience of local communities. • More adaptable institutions to changing conditions. • More flexible institutions that can be altered to work in different contexts.
Anticipatory	Long-term planning and foresight thinking are institutionalized. Known and unknown risks and opportunities are considered, analyzed and planned for.	Produces plans and steps to prepare and prevent consequences of unexpected risks. Enhances knowledge, capacity and flexibility for disturbance.	

Attributes (qualities or capacities)	General characteristics or inputs (capacity)	Idealized outputs (functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (performance)
Adaptive	Spaces for reflection and deliberation are institutionalized. Processes exist to revisit and evolve policies, institutions and adapt actions.	Ensures that management plans and actions are being actively adapted to reflect changing social-ecological contexts and new knowledge.	
Innovative	Innovation and experimentation is encouraged and success and failures are monitored. A higher risk tolerance is embodied.	Allows change to be seen as an opportunity. Enables new and more effective ideas and actions to emerge.	
Flexible	Policies exist that recognize the need to downscale environmental management and conservation models to fit local realities. Efforts are taken to understand and document about the diverse contexts where policies are applied and to deliberate on necessary adjustments.	Enables governance systems and management models to be adjusted to better fit with local social, cultural, political, economic and environmental contexts.	

D. Robust governance – (Legitimate, Connected, Nested and Polycentric.)

Attributes (qualities or capacities)	General characteristics or inputs (capacity)	Idealized outputs (functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (performance)
Legitimate	A collective vision shapes policies and guides actions at all scales. Institutional legitimacy is conferred (e.g., in policy) and perceived (e.g., by constituents). Governors act with integrity and consistency. Institutions are transparent.	Ascertains that there is support from above and that there is a supportive constituency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutions are strengthened and well supported. • Institutional performance and functioning is more or less consistent. • Institutions persist over time.
Connected	Networks of organizations and actors are strongly linked vertically and horizontally. Bridging organizations are present. Processes are in place to support network development, to develop social relations and to support mutual learning.	Helps to bridge between and across scales. Creates supportive community, produces social capital, fosters respect and trust and builds social memory. Encourages communication, information exchange, enables diffusion of innovations, and facilitates collaboration.	

Attributes (qualities or capacities)	General characteristics or inputs (capacity)	Idealized outputs (functioning)	Idealized Outcomes (performance)
Polycentric	Decision-making and action taking centers in multiple places, across jurisdictions and at multiple scales interact and cohere towards a common goal. Institutions are present that are diverse and redundant - that serve similar purposes and have overlapping jurisdictions and functions.	Helps to buffer against change in one location. Ensures that the governance system does not collapse when faced with adversity or crises.	
Nested	Tasks are assigned to appropriate levels. Decision-making authority and responsibility are conferred to the lowest level possible. Self-organization is encouraged and supported. Authority and responsibility is supported by adequate state or other outside support (legal recognition, political will, time commitment) and oversight.	Empowers appropriate entity to take necessary action. Allows also for shaping and adapting institutions and decision-making processes to different local sub-contexts (social circumstances, governance, ecologies) within larger system.	

Appendix F

Sample Questions for interviews

The following questions were based on the framework in Appendix 5 to gather evidence on each of the attributes in the framework.

Governance Attribute	Questions	Notes
Effective – Policies and laws support maintenance of system integrity and functioning	Do you think the scope, goals, and aims of CPA 2018 are comprehensive, clearly articulated and communicated to stakeholders. If yes, please give examples.	
	Are there clear definition and boundaries on action and milestones set for achieving success? Are there indicators of successful policy implementation? If yes, please give examples.	
	Who are the stakeholders of CPA 2018? Do CPA 2018 and other related policies and processes ensure acknowledgement of, respect for and incorporation of diverse perspectives, values, cultures and rights. Including views of marginalized and vulnerable groups are considered, like SMEs. If yes, please give examples.	
Equitable – Employs inclusive processes and produces fair outcomes	Are cost and benefits allocation (carbon tax revenue and GHG reduction) defined and documented in form of policy and publicly available?	
	Are the monitoring, evaluation, reflections and communication of performance institutionalized? Are there processes and platforms in place to co-produce knowledge and enhance social and institutional memory? Please give examples.	
Responsive – Enables adaptation to diverse contexts and changing conditions.	Are there plans and steps prepared to prevent consequences of unexpected risks?	
Robust – Ensures functioning institutions persist, maintain performance and cope with perturbations and crises.	Who is the main coordinating body or unit for the implementation of CPA 2018? Are the roles, functions, and mandates of different governments, agencies and organizations coordinated? Are meeting frequencies and minutes of meetings documented and available?	

Appendix G

List of Private sector support and initiatives on Climate Action and Carbon Pricing

- **Industry Sectors (listed issuers and large non-listed companies in Singapore) -** Corporate Social Responsibility, ESG reporting, Mandatory Climate Reporting
- **Building & Construction** – Green Mark Certification and Green Building Certifications
- **Global Compact Network Singapore (GCNS)** – Singapore chapter of the UN Global Compact
- **NGOs** – e.g. Singapore Youth for Climate Action, Nature Society of Singapore, World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)
- **Academe** – National University of Singapore, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore Polytechnic, Newcastle Australia Institute of Higher Education Center for Sustainable Development
- **Financial Institutions / Banks** – Economic Development Board (EDB), Development Bank of Singapore (DBS), United Overseas Bank (UOB), Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation (HSBC)
- **Main-stream and social Media** – Channel News Asia (CAN), Singapore Press Holdings, Mediacorp

Appendix H

Sample Questionnaire for High GHG Emitters, SMEs and General Public

Group	Survey Questions	Y/N Remarks
Effective governance – Policies and laws support maintenance of system integrity and functioning		
High Emitters and SMEs	Do you understand and agree with the rationale for implementing the carbon pricing in Singapore?	
	Do you know which government agency or agencies to engage should you have concerns and suggestions regarding CPA implementation?	
	Did you receive adequate training and support while preparing your monitoring plans and emissions reports?	
	Is 25,000 tons emissions threshold to pay carbon tax adequate to push for changes in operational efficiency or shift to low carbon technology?	
Public	Do you understand and agree with the rationale for implementing the carbon pricing in Singapore?	
	Do you know your role in reducing emissions of GHG?	
Equitable governance – Employs inclusive processes and produces fair outcomes		
High Emitter & SMEs	Was your company invited to participate in public forums and consultation on CPA implementation?	
	Were your concerns on carbon pricing implementation addressed adequately? List your concern in the remarks.	
	Do you think the time allocated to increase carbon tax adequate for your company to take necessary reduction measures?	
SMEs	As an SME, do you agree with reducing the emission threshold? What are your reasons and your proposed emissions threshold? – state this in the remarks.	
Public	Is information about climate change and carbon pricing readily available and accessible?	
	As an individual, did you participate in public consultation about CPA implementation? If yes, did you hear back on the outcome of your suggestion or query?	
Responsive governance – Enables adaptation to diverse contexts and changing conditions.		Y/N Remarks
High Emitters & SMEs	Do you think access to new technologies and research is accessible and readily available?	
	Do you know how carbon pricing policy performance is monitored, evaluated and is it communicated to all?	
	If your company has known of a technology(ies) or measure to reduce GHG emission, are you able to share this with others who may benefit this technology?	

Group	Survey Questions	Y/N Remarks
	If your company has known of a technology(ies) or measure to reduce GHG emission, do you know how to seek for government assistance if you need it?	
Public	Do you feel there is enough assistance from government to reduce electricity and water consumption? State in remarks what assistance you have availed so far.	
	If as a member of the public you have known of a technology(ies) or measure to reduce GHG emission, do you know who to reach out to share this information?	
Robust governance – Ensures functioning institutions persist, maintain performance and cope with perturbations and crises.		
High Emitters	Do you have to deal with more than one government agency regarding carbon pricing and carbon tax compliance? State in remarks the name of the agency(s) you deal with.	
High emitters & SMEs	Do you believe that the government will act should Carbon Pricing and other climate change actions become too demanding and hurt companies' financial and competitive advantage?	
Public	Do you trust that the government has the best interest of its citizens in driving climate change mitigation measures?	